

International Journal of

Indagare

Available online at www.indgr.org

Pregnancy Complication and Prenatal Threat Associated with the Risk of Mental Retardation.

Author: Shaheen Islam

DOI:

Citation: Islam, S. (2000). Pregnancy Complication and Prenatal Threat Associated with the Risk of Mental Retardation. Dhaka Univ. J. Psychol., 24, 1-8.

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of pregnancy complications and prenatal threats as potential risk factors for the prevalence of mental retardation in children. Utilizing data from an epidemiological study on childhood disabilities in Bangladesh, the medical histories of 10,000 children aged 2 to 9 years were analyzed. A two-stage screening and professional evaluation process identified 101 children with serious disabilities, including 46 with serious mental retardation (SMR). Risk analysis using logistic regression revealed a significant positive association between prenatal threats during the first trimester (such as high blood pressure, bleeding, and infection) and the occurrence of SMR, with exposed mothers facing a 2.73 times higher probability of having a child with mental retardation. However, the study failed to establish a significant association between reproductive loss, measured via gravidity, parity, and miscarriage and mental retardation or other developmental disabilities.

Keywords: Mental Retardation; Prenatal Threat; Pregnancy Complication; Childhood Disability

PREGNANCY COMPLICATION AND PRENATAL THREAT ASSOCIATED WITH THE RISK OF MENTAL RETARDATION

Shaheen Islam

Department of Psychology
University of Dhaka.

ABSTRACT

The issue of pregnancy complication and prenatal threat as an associated risk factor for the prevalence of mental retardation was investigated in the present study. The data from the medical history of 10,000 children of 2 to 9 years of age, collected during an epidemiological study on childhood disabilities in Bangladesh, were analyzed. The result indicated the significance of prenatal threat as a potential risk factor for the occurrence of mental retardation. The study, however, failed to contend the effect of reproductive loss on mental retardation.

INTRODUCTION

Considerable document on the impact of detrimental prenatal conditions and pregnancy complication in elevating the risk of mental retardation and other childhood disabilities had been offered by the researcher. During early period of cell division and multiplication, numerous genetic and environmental influence could cause dysmorphic events (Lamont and Dennis, 1988; Rao, 1990; Rubin and Davis, 1986). Taylor, Nelson and Howie (1993) examined the antecedents of 294 children with neurodevelopmental disability and found significantly higher incidence of prenatal complications among the disabled children than among their matched normal developing siblings of nearest ordinal position. Livanainen and Lahdevirta (1988) reported that infectious diseases alone caused mental retardation in 11.1%

and other neurological sequelae in 1.5% of 1,000 children examined. Viral prenatal infection like rubella, syphilis, influenza in prenatal period could also lead to infants born blind, deaf, retarded, cerebral palsied, microcephalic and with congenital heart defects (Pass, Stagno, and Myers, 1980; Koterazawa, Shimogaki, Miyata, Uetani, Nakamura, 1994). Regarding viral infection and drug, the time of invasion was crucial. Consequences of these diseases were more serious during the first trimester of pregnancy, when the fetus has no detectable immunological response. To a certain extent pregnancy complication was also found to be an important factor in severe mental retardation in the studies of Drillien (1978) and Hagberg (1978). Since adverse prenatal conditions have been documented to be positively associated with mental retardation and various other childhood disabilities, present study addressed certain

prenatal issues as a potential risk factor. The objectives of the study were :

1) Pregnancy complications : Whether number of gravidity, parity, or miscarriage had any association with the occurrence of mental retardation or other childhood disabilities.

2) Prenatal threat : Whether manifestation of any adverse conditions such as high blood pressure, bleeding, infection/fever, or other health problems during pregnancy raised the risk of mental retardation or other childhood disabilities.

METHOD

Sample and Methodology

Present study utilized the data collected during a population based study on childhood disability carried out in five selected areas of Bangladesh. Detail sampling technique and procedure involved have been furnished in Durkin et al., (1991, 1992); Zaman et. al., (1990, 1992). In brief the study involved :

1. Two stage design to screen and diagnose children with five types of disabilities (mental retardation,

visual, hearing, motor, and seizure).

2. 10299 children of 2-9 years of age were screened in the first stage following a modified cluster sampling technique from two urban and three rural areas of Bangladesh.
3. Children screened positive for disability and a random sample of 8% children with negative screening results were examined by a team of professional. 84.8% of the children referred from the first stage were actually evaluated and taken as the sample of the present study. Number of clusters and children screened in rural and urban area has been presented in Table-I.

Overall, 8.2% of the children were screened positive, and 18.6% were referred for professional evaluation. Age and gender distribution of children evaluated by the professional have been presented in Table -II: 46.5% of the children professionally evaluated were of positive screening results.

Instruments

In the first stage of the study, a ten items short simple screening questionnaire, the

TABLE - I

Number of Clusters, Children Screened, and % of Boys by Habitat :

Area	Clusters	Children screened	% of Boys
Urban	30	5103	52.8
Rural	35	5196	52.9

Ten Questions (TQ), was used to identify five types of disabilities (Zaman, et. al. , 1990). A Household Form (HF) and a Mother-Child Form (MC) questionnaires were also filled in to gather demographic and maternal history. In the following second stage, a Medical Assessment Form (MAF) developed by Davison, et. al., in 1986 (Durkin, 1991) was used by the physicians for detail medical evaluation to record the diagnosis and disability ratings following standard criteria. It contained detail medical history which includes questions regarding pregnancy complication and prenatal threat. Other standard psychological tests ie., Childhood Disability Questionnaire (CDQ) by Belmont (1984) , Independent Behaviour Assessment Scale (IBAS) by Munir (1986) and five non-verbal test of Stanford Bient Intelligence Scale (Huq, 1991) were also used for psychological diagnosis of mental retardation.

physicians in the second stage. Pregnancy history covering the issue of number of gravidity, parity, stillbirths, and spontaneous abortions the mother had, whether the mother had high blood pressure, bleeding, infection/ fever or any other health problems in Ist trimester, reported by the mother were recorded in MAF. The pregnancy and prenatal history utilized in this study as probable risk factors have been documented in the figure I. The diagnosis of presence and severity of mental retardation was made jointly by the physicians and psychologists after each had examined the child separately.

For risk factor analysis odd ratios calculated through logistic regression method taking account of the two- phase design of the study was made on the

TABLE - II
Age and Gender Distribution of Children Evaluated.

Age Group	All	Boys	Girls
2-5 years	732	386	346
6-9 years	894	518	376
Total	1626 (100%)	904 (56%)	722(44%)

Procedure

Thorough medical and psychological examinations were carried out to identify disabled children. Medical Assessment Form (MAF) designed to cover various aspects of pregnancy and child's prenatal history were dully filled in by the

weighted subsample of children who were professionally evaluated. Average weight was assigned to each case depending on its TQ status. Odd ratio greater than 1 indicated the children with the associated factor has greater risk of having disability than those without the factor.

Figure I : Documentation of pregnancy complication and prenatal threat as variable for risk factor.

Pregnancy Complication : (before birth of this child)		
Item 1 :	Number of gravidity	Total count
Item 2 :	Number of parity	Total count
Item 3 :	Number of stillbirth	Total count
	Number of abortion	
Prenatal Threat : (during pregnancy with this child)		
Item 4 :	High blood pressure	yes (3) Unknown (2) No (1)
	Bleeding within first trimester	
	Infection/fever within first trimester	
	other health problems	

RESULTS

Number and percentage of different levels of disabled children and normal children after professional evaluation in rural and urban areas have been presented in table III.

The present study considered only the children suffering from serious disability. Number of mentally retarded children and

children with other development disabilities in the present study have been presented in Table 1V.

In total 101 children were found to have serious disabilities, of which 46 children were suffering from serious mental retardation (SMR) and 55 from other developmental disabilities (ODD). The estimated prevalence of serious mental retardation and other developmental

TABLE - III

Number of disabled, Seriously Disabled and and Normal children in the study.

Area	Any Disability	Serious Disability	Children Having No Disability
Rural	114	47	758
Urban	108	54	646

disabilities were 5.93 and 9.74 per thousand, respectively (Islam, 1996-97).

Table V and VI gave the rural/urban distribution of pregnancy complication and prenatal threat in first trimester. Percentage of gravidity and parity, both were high in rural area (48.2% and 47.3%, respectively). Gravidity was defined as the

investigated separately as indicative of complication during pregnancy.

As expected high blood pressure was high in urban area (1.8%), while bleeding in the 1st trimester (0.5%) and other health problems (10.6%), saving infection/fever were high in rural area. Occurrence of any

TABLE - IV

Number of Children with Serious Mental Retardation and Other Developmental Disability

Number of Children	Serious Mental Retardation		Other Developmental Disabilities	
	Boy	Girl	Boy	Girl
Total	25	21	25	30
Grand Total	46		55	

* Other Developmental Disabilities include motor, visual, hearing, and seizure

total number of pregnancies before this child and counting this child, while Parity was defined as the total number of live birth before this child and counting this child. Though overall percentage of stillbirth and abortion were low in the study population, these conditions were also more typical of rural population. Due to little variability, stillbirth and abortion were considered together in the present analyses. Gravidity and parity were

such problem during 1st trimester was considered as prenatal threat.

The distribution of pregnancy complication and prenatal threat for Serious Mental Retardation (SMR) and other. Developmental Disabilities have been presented in Table VII. This Table showed no notable difference among the mean number of gravidity and parity for all the groups. Incidence of miscarriage

TABLE - V

Pattern of Pregnancy Complication by Area (%)

Area	Gravidity (3 or more)	Parity (3 or more)	Stillbirth (atleast one)	Abortion (atleast one)
Rural	63.0	61.9	0.6	0.4
Urban	58.6	55.2	0.0	0.2

TABLE VI
Various Prenatal Threat by Area (%)

Area	Blood Pressure	Bleeding	Infection/ Fever	Other Problems
Rural	0.4	0.5	0.3	10.6
Urban	1.8	0.3	0.6	5.2

was relatively higher for SMR (9.7) than ODD. Similarly, incidence of prenatal threat was also comparatively high for SMR.

Table VIII : presented the point estimated of the odd ratios for selected medical factors indicating association with serious mental retardation or other serious childhood disabilities.

Among the various risk factors studied prenatal threat was found to be significantly associated with SMR. No significant positive relationship with ODD were observed for any of the factors.

DISCUSSION

The importance of mother's health during pregnancy as having influence on the growth and development of the child had been an usual conviction (Taylor, et. al 1993; Livananen and Lahdevirta, 1988;

Pass, et al (1980; Koterazawa et al, 1994). Supporting the view, the present study reported that mothers who experienced greater threat like 'high blood pressure', 'bleeding' in the 1st trimester, 'infection' or any other problem during the prenatal period had 2.73 time more probability of having mentally retarded children than those without any such threat. The first trimester is a critical period in the development of brain, therefore, while in utero, the fetus is at increased risk of mental retardation from maternal disease, infection or any other problem. However, no significant association between reproductive loss as indicated by gravidity, parity, and miscarriage, with severe mental retardation was established by the present results (Table VIII). Since it had been shown in various studies that there was a tendency for a repetition of some forms of reproductive casualties in the mother (Lilienfeld and Pasamanick, 1955), no

TABLE VII
Pregnancy Complication and Prenatal Risk Factors for SMR, ODD, and Children with No Disability (%)

Group	Gravidity (X)	Parity (X)	Miscarriage (%)	Prenatal Threat (%)
SMR (N=46)	3.8	3.6	9.7	15.2
ODD(N=55)	3.4	3.2	7.3	9.1
General Children	3.6	3.5	7.6	10.0

*ODD include motor, vision, hearing and seizure.

TABLE VIII
Point Estimates of Crude Odd Ratios Indicating Possible Associations between Selected Medical Factors with Mental Retardation and Other Developmental Disabilities.

Medical Risk Factors	Serious Mental Retardation (SMR)	Other Developmental Disabilities (ODD)*
Gravidity	1.19 (0.93-1.53)	0.94 (0.86-1.02)
Parity	1.19 (0.91-1.55)	0.87 (0.86-1.02)
Miscarriage	0.89 (0.55-1.45)	0.58 (0.27-1.26)
Prenatal Threat	2.73 (1.18-6.29)	0.68 (0.25-1.67)

*ODD include motor, vision, hearing and seizure.

ready explanation could be offered for absence of similar association. Taylor and his associates (1985) found strong association between severe mental retardation and severe hypertension, however they failed to find any significant association between disability and vaginal bleeding before 12 weeks' gestation. Nonetheless, the lower bound confidence interval above 0.90 for gravidity and parity implied remote possibility of some association with severe mental retardation suggesting more rigorous study in this respect.

Role of pregnancy complication in the aetiology of other forms of neurodevelopmental disabilities has been less well studied. However, data of Taylor et al., (1985, 1993) suggest that pregnancy and delivery complication may in many cases lead to neurodevelopmental disabilities. Contradicting the former notion, other developmental disabilities were not found to have any significant positive association with any reproductive loss or prenatal threat. This might imply that such adverse conditions were more effective in raising the risk for serious mental retardation rather than other developmental

disabilities. Another conjecture might be that specific causes were often more responsible for specific type of disability, but since all other forms of developmental disabilities i.e., motor, visual, hearing, and seizure, were embraced into single category in the present study, the effect, if any, might have either been nullified or not been revealed. Absence of any indication on the frequency of damage in central nervous system due to prenatal and perinatal condition might as well be a rationale for the apparent low risk found for other developmental disabilities.

In conclusion, the analysis of prenatal and pregnancy complication as potential risk factors in the present study heightened the importance of the role played by the medical dimension in explaining and predicting mental retardation. It suggests that use of various prenatal risk inventories to screen infant and children would be highly beneficial for early detection and also to predict long term consequence in child health and development programme in our country. Furthermore, the author duly recognizes the necessity for considering effect of social class and habitat (rural/urban) on the presence of

different prenatal risk factors because a strong relationship between the two had repeatedly been perceived.

REFERENCE

- Belmont, L (1984) The International Pilot Study of Severe Childhood Disability : Final report : Screening for severe mental retardation in developing countries, Utrecht, Netherland: Bishop Beckers Institute.
- Drillien CM (1978) Aetiology of severe handicapping conditions in early childhood. In Elliot K, O'Connor M Eds Major Mental handicap: Methods and cost of prevention, North-Holland, Amsterdam, Oxford, New York : Elsevier Excerpta Medica, 17-27.
- Durkin M S, Davidson L L, Hasan M, Hasan Z, Hauser W A, Khan H, Paul T J, and Shourt P E (1992) Estimates of the prevalence of childhood seizure disorder in population where professional resources are scarce : Results from Bangladesh, Jamaica and Pakistan, Paediatric and Perinatal Epidemiology, 6, 166-180.
- Durkin M, Zaman S, Thrburn M, Hasan M, and Davidson L (1991) Population-based studies of childhood disability in developing countries : Rational and study design. Int. J. Ment. Health 20 (3) 47-
- Hagberg B (1978) Severe mental retardation in Swedish children born 1959-1970 : epidemiological panorama and causative factors, In Elliot K, O'Connor M Eds Major mental handicap : Methods and cost of prevention, North-Holland, Amsterdam, Oxford, New York : Elsevier Excerpta Medica, 29-51.
- Huq S (1992) Determination of reliability and validity of Stanford Binet Intelligence Scale and the construction of norms for use in Bangladesh, Unpublished Ph. D Dissertation, Dhaka, University.
- Koterazawa K, Shimogaki K, Miyata H, Uetani Y, Nakamura H, (1994) A study on the causes of the physical and mental disabilities in children, No-To-Hattatsu Jan; 26 (1) : 9-13.
- Islam, S, (1996-97) Deliberation on childhood Disability : Its Prevalence, The Bangladesh Journal of Psychology, 16, 23-22.
- Lamont M A and Dennis N R (1988) Aetiology of mild retardation Arch Dis Child. Se; 63 (9) : 1032-8.
- Lillienfeld A M and Pasamanick B (1955) the association of maternal and fetal factors with the development of mental, Journal of American Mental Association 159, 155-160.
- Livanainen M, Lahdevirta J (1988) Infectious diseases as causes of mental retardation and other concomitant neurological sequelae, Australia and New Zealand Journal of Developmental Disabilities 14 (3-4) 201-210.
- Munir S Z (1990) Development of a Adaptive Behaviour Scale, Paper presented at the 10th Asian Conference on Mental Retardation held in Karachi, Pakistan.
- Pass R F, Sragno S, Myers G.J., (198) Outcome of symptomatic congenital cytomegalovirus infection. Pediatrics, 66, 758.
- Rao J M (1990) A population based study of mild mental handicap in children: preliminary analysis. J Ment-Defic-Res. Fbe : 34 (pt1) : 59-65.
- Rubin I L and Davis M (1986) Etiology of developmental disabilities in Soweto, South Africa. Am-J-Public-Health Sep : 76 (9) : 112-4.
- Taylor D J, Howie P W, Davidson J, Davidson D, Drillien CM (1985) Do pregnancy complications contribute to neurodevelopmental disability? Lancet Mar. 30; 1 (8431) : 713-6.
- Taylor D J, Nelson J and Howie P W (1993) Neurodevelopmental disability-a sibling-control study. Dev-Med-Child-Neurol. 35 (11) : 957-64.
- Zaman S S, Khan N, Islam S, Banu S, Dixit S, Shrouf P and Durkin M (1990) Validity of the ten questions for screening serious childhood disability : Results from urban Bangladesh. International Journal of Epidemiology, 19, 613-620.
- Zaman S S, Khan N Z, Islam S, and Durkin M (1992) Childhood Disabilities in Bangladesh: Report on rapid epidemiological assessment of childhood disabilities in Bangladesh, 1992 Bangladesh Protibondhi foundation.